

Creating an Authentic Learning Environment Using e-Learning Application

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Abstract: Use of mobile devices is an essential component of e-learning. Adopting an authentic learning approach via e-learning applications can help students better understanding and memorisation of concepts. This study presents analysis from a survey of students (n=79) enrolled in The University of Queensland to investigate the relationship between the ability to understand and memorise the scientific concepts with prior experience of using an authentic e-learning system. The results indicated that students show the same level of understanding and experience the ability to memorise the concepts taught in the application irrespective of having or not having any prior experience of using such applications. The implications of these results can be useful to the professionals who design the authentic learning curriculum and develop e-learning systems.

Keywords: e-learning, applications, authentic, learning

1. Introduction

Authentic learning is a broad range of educational and instructional techniques that focuses on connecting what students have learned in the school to real-world issues, problems, and applications (concepts). It can be freely created in classroom settings and university and is preferable to web-based delivery. The possibility to practice authentic learning in universities is high as the internet, and web-supported learning is ubiquitous at universities (Jan Herrington, Reeves, and Oliver, 2009). However, regrettably higher education today does not encourage inventive thinking that is essential to endorse authentic learning and are unwilling to test the theories and methods already used to enhance students learning experience because sometimes experiments or practical ideas are too complex or risky to be done in the classroom (Lombardi, 2007).

1.1 Structure

In the present world, it is essential to realise that authentic learning delivers knowledge and depends on technology and the tools used for education. In this way, e-learning uses the authentic approach to maximise its productivity, and this approach uses e-learning tools to establish the method of learning using those instruments. E-learning can be defined as "utilisation of electronic technologies to access educational curriculum outside of a traditional classroom" (Mayer, 2014; Moreno and Mayer, 1999). Learning in universities has conventionally disconnected knowing and doing. Learners in universities usually solve problems with codes, because of which the object represented is lost (Resnick, 1987). While in authentic learning, learners use the physical components of a case to solve the problem. Students only learn from information and communication technologies (ICTs) provided in universities instead with them as cognitive tools (D. H. Jonassen, Reeves, Hong, Harvey, and Peters, 1997; Kim and Reeves, 2007). 'Cognitive tools' which is the theoretical foundation for 'learning with' approach has been developed to act as academic companions to facilitate higher-order learning and critical thinking (D. Jonassen, Carr, and Lajoie, 2000). (D. H. Jonassen et al., 1997) described the theoretical basis of cognitive tools, defining them as "thinking tools that intensify, extend, and rearrange mental powers to help learners in problem-solving and constructing their realities". In this approach, learners that use technology as a tool act as creators to analyse, interpret, organise, and represent their knowledge to others. In the past thirty years, significant international attention is on higher education effectiveness to make students competent for the workplace through proper teaching practices (Billett, 2009; Van Koller, 2010). In higher education, the focus is mainly on disciplinary learning, as a result of which students are unable to practice this knowledge in different contexts when needed (J. S. Brown, Collins, and Duguid, 1989; Jan Herrington et al., 2009; Lave and Wenger, 1991). (Janice Herrington, Mantei, Herrington, Olney, and Ferry, 2008; Lombardi, 2007) discussed that emerging technology allows authentic learning as it promotes teamwork across distance, communication with experts, results sharing and access to research communities online. Such technologies promote collaboration (digital databases, social networking tools and referencing tools), enable joint construction of knowledge (role plays,

problem-based activities, case-based learning, discussion forums and virtual communities of practice) and allow an individual or group articulation (blogs, e-portfolios and video-capture devices)(Jan Herrington et al., 2009; Lombardi, 2007).

1.2 Literature review

The importance of education is undeniable. Moreover, the inclusion of technology in education systems is a social imperative that will be adopted by all education systems eventually (Lazar, 2015). The dissatisfaction of students in education settings determines a necessity to consider the student's commitment level (Delialioğlu, 2012). In the study by (Wang, Shen, Novak, and Pan, 2009), the learners' commitment was noticeably higher in mobile-learning or e-learning environments because they were active learners. It has been found that authentic learning motivates the students despite the challenges involved (Lombardi, 2007). There are many domains of e-learning and education, but this article focuses on suggesting a new method of authentic learning with a proposed mobile application, Authentic Lab. It is well-known that learning by practising is one of the most effective ways to learn but implementing the authentic learning has been challenging for years because sometimes the experiments were complicated or dangerous (Prunuske, Wick, and Wolyniak, 2015) and some utterly impossible to perform (Lombardi, 2007). The advancement of technology has provided means that can provide students with lots of ease and assistance for equipping themselves with the safe and relatively secure setting of authentic learning. The authentic learning majorly focuses on real-world problems, along with that; it proposes solutions to these problems (Lombardi, 2007). (Churchill, 2007) states that technology amplifies our intellectual and physical capacity and is potentially an important part of school education. An authentic learning environment must be able to provide authentic concepts and practical contexts so that students can assimilate the knowledge with the alignment of efficient use of that knowledge in real-life (J. S. Brown et al., 1989). Such a learning environment yields confidence in the students as it prepares them to face similar problems and situations in a professional setting. Moreover, the authentic learning environment should provide the learner with authentic activities (D. H. Jonassen, 1985). Another prominent trait of the authentic environment is the provision of access to expert opinions and processes and designing of the actual operations (Lave and Wenger, 1991). It only means that in the learning process of history, students can play skits and assume the roles of the personalities they are supposed to remember, or they can form a forum and have a debate about some topic that happened centuries ago, under the supervision of their mentor/teacher. Such learning methods play a vital role in enhancing cognitively higher learning. The authentic learning environment also provides multiple functions and varied perspectives in studies (Bransford, Sherwood, Hasselbring, Kinzer, and Williams, 1990).

The environment should be supportive of collaborative work and concept exchange (A. L. Brown, 1992) for it induces teamwork tendencies and sharpens the cognitive abilities for the leadership roles. Students do not just perform homework together but assume a position in a team and work with their mates as an integral part of the group in an authentic environment. The technique of scaffolding and fading of the mentor in the classroom can help the learner to be independent (J. S. Brown et al., 1989; Greenfield, 1984).The researchers indicated that in the process of learning, there are several factors at play. These factors include Self-Efficacy, Perceived Enjoyment (Abdullah and Ward, 2016), Overall Experience (Braund and Reiss, 2006), Technology Anxiety and Social Influence (Jan Herrington et al., 2009). Researchers use the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) to analyse the stated factors. Literature also showed a meta-analysis project that presented good results while using the TAM. The study indicated that TAM's application to the e-learning paradigm gives valid and promising results (King and He, 2006). Another research exhibited that TAM is the theory used the most when it comes to the e-learning frameworks; with 86% of studies using TAM (ŠUmak, HeričKo, and PušNik, 2011).

Apart from TAM, other models are also developed. In a research study conducted at BDMU a theoretical framework based on TAM was used. The researchers used a questionnaire that extracted information from many (n=153) students who were already using online learning modules in their institute. In that study, the conclusive results exhibited that ease of use of technology, attitude towards e-learning and social influence of the students were among the key factors to adopt e-learning. To understand and improve the e-learning experience, Alexander proposed the Four-Level Model, where the first level suggests online presentation and publishing (V. Chang, 2016). Subsequent level deals with online quizzes/ assessments, forms were allowing students to give feedback about teachers and the last level deal with interactive learning combining benefits of all the other levels. (MacDonald, Stodel, Farres, Breithaupt, and Gabriel, 2001) proposed a demand-driven model of e-learning. According to this model, the material should be research-based, comprehensive and valid. The delivery of the content should be via the means of the web, and a user-friendly e-learning user interface (UI) should be

in the place. The instructional design model is a combination of theories proposed by different researchers (V. Chang, 2016; Conrad, 2000; Mishra, 2002). This model is composed of several components. Prominent of these are demand for domain knowledge, need for the online curriculum, prior experience, computer knowledge, e-learning tools, teacher training, delivery methods and technological infrastructure. Garrison proposed an inquiry model, which presented the teachers and tutors with a detailed understanding of traits of e-learning. Bates provided the ACTIONS model (Wagner, 1998) which links e-Learning to aspects of Access, Costs, Teaching Methods, Interaction and user-friendliness, Organisational issues, Novelty and speed of course adaptation.

2. Methodology

The study formulates a methodology to create an application based on authentic learning principles. Application incorporates realistic cases in its presentation. The survey questions based on real-life examples were presented in the application. It allows the study to evaluate the efficiency of authentic attributes. It also aims to have results about the ability of the sample to understand and remember the concepts discussed in the application. The application is named 'Authentic Lab'. In the development of the graphical user interface, wireframe layouts are used with the specifications given in Table 1.

Table 1: Graphical user interface specifications

S No.	Specification	Value
1	Dimensions	1536 × 2048 pixels
2	Navigation buttons	4
3	Transition	Slide left, slide-right
4	Dimensions of icons used	128 × 128 pixels.
5	Number of sub-screens	7
6	Total screens	4
7	Font Source	Sans Pro
8	Font size:	25 pixels

As mentioned, there are four screens, which presents four basic scientific concepts. It is observed that on an average, a user takes 17.5 interactions to navigate through the application. Navigation through the application is based on a single entry-exit approach with inter page navigation capability. Deliberately the design of the application is kept simple to keep the focus on the learning content, its presentation and measurement of the recorded responses. This allows the user to respond to questions based on solely on the quality, order, and merit of the material and its arrangement. The design is also kept simple so that the user might not indulge into other design details of the application. In this study, different user flows are used for user interaction with the application. These user flows have different learning outcomes incorporating them with various real-time problem statements. User flows and their results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: User flow and outcomes

User Flow	Concept	Question	Learning	Outcome
	Loading Page	Main Screen	Presentation Screen	Aim
1	Egg Float Test	If he/she knows the difference between a healthy and rotten chicken egg	The screens followed by this preface presented the user with video aids and graphical representation of the concepts.	This concept aimed to supply the information about Hydrogen; connecting the scientific knowledge about Hydrogen in a real-world problem.
2	Paper bag Magic	If he/she knows how to ripen the fruits fast and naturally	Preface presented the user with video aids and graphical representation of the concepts.	Hydrogen was discussed comprehensively. This concept aimed to supply information about Hydrogen and measure how much the user understands
3	Paper bag Magic	if he/she knows how to save the vegetables from turning into slug-green while cooking.	It presented the user with video aids and graphical representation of the concepts.	The aim was to let the user learn about Magnesium.
4	Car Screens	if he/she knows why people use car screens in summers.	It presented the user with video aids and graphical representation of the concepts.	The aim was to make the user learn about greenhouse gasses.

Figure 1, Figure 2, Figure 3, and Figure 4 shows the flow of cases representing graphical user interfaces of four screenplays.

Figure 1: User workflow.1 of Authentic Lab

Figure 2: User workflow.2 of Authentic Lab

Figure 3: User workflow.3 of Authentic Lab

Figure 4: User workflow.4 of Authentic Lab

3. Results and discussion

A survey method was used to measure the efficacy of the authentic learning application developed at The University of Queensland, Brisbane, Australia. Eighty-nine students participated in the survey. The respondents belonged to three different academic background levels; bachelors, masters, and PhD and their age ranged from 18 to 38 years. As shown in the Figure 5, only 25% had a previous understanding of these concepts, whereas majority of the respondents (73%) did not know the ideas presented in the authentic lab application. Most of the respondents with the prior learning experience of e-learning application came from the bachelor's program and age group 23-27 years old.

Figure 5: Age group comparison for prior e-learning experience

A comprehensive analysis of ease to use and recollection was done against the age, prior experience, and level of education. When ease of understanding and extent of remembering the concept were compared among the participants having previous knowledge and no experience, it was found that inexperienced participants practised the same level of ease of understanding and rated similar levels of likelihood of remembering the concepts as shown in Figure 6. That suggests that e-learning platforms are user-friendly and efficient to be used by anyone. The measured parameters did not vary significantly between participants of different ages and education level as well showing a favourable response to the usage of the app and a satisfactory level of effectiveness of the app in teaching concepts based on the principles of authentic learning. This study indicates that the ease of understanding the concept and remembering it was independent of the age group, educational level and prior experience of using an e-learning application as shown in Figure 7. The first noteworthy conclusion can be that the method of developing the application and presenting the user with authentic content was successful, and users with or without prior of an e-learning application knowledge performed equally well on the survey questions. The other important conclusion from results is that the nature of the content was not challenging enough. Keeping this possibility in mind, researchers, in future, can use relatively tricky concepts. The researchers can also use a different field of knowledge as well (Maths, Physics). Another inference from results is that rather than using difficult content or varied field of study, the attributes of authentic learning can be changed to see some significant difference in the results.

Figure 6: E-learning ease and remembering analysis for different age groups

Figure 7: E-learning ease and remembering analysis for different experience groups

4. Suggestions and future directions

According to this research, a learning method presenting higher-level concepts can give promising results. These concepts can be designed according to the field of study, Biology, Physics or Maths. In the modern era of technology and social media, the e-learning can be modified to enhance the e-learning experience. According to (Moore, Dickson-Deane, and Galyen, 2011), the sharing of ideas, access of the community to learn and convey concepts can improve the e-learning concepts while others believe it can be enhanced with personalisation of e-learning experience (Klašnja-Milićević, Vesin, and Ivanović, 2018). This research shows that a customisable and social-media friendly e-learning platform can be designed and developed that allows people to use social-media links and friendships to link with a more significant and useful group of people. This possibility can also lead to the bigger platform endorsing the unlimited number of tutors with likes and comments as to other forms of social media (De Vries, Gensler, and Leeflang, 2012). Such platforms allow easy access to a variety of expert tutelage, which is an attribute of authentic learning (C.-T. Chang, Hajiyeve, and Su, 2017; Cidral, Oliveira, Di Felice, and Aparicio, 2018). This way, social media integration can provide a source of expert availability and fulfil one of the critical attributes of authentic learning.

About the limitations of the e-learning platforms, many changes are possible in the provision of e-learning. The lack of socialisation can be solved by enhancing the scope of the online community. Some features like built-in audio and video conversation and use of latest technology in terms of real-time learning of concepts (in the field of Geography, Aerospace Sciences) can serve a purpose of motivation for the learners. Authentic learning consists of multiple items, including relevance, sustained investigation, various resources and perspectives, collaboration, reflection, integrated assessment. In this study, only a few were integrated into the Authentic Lab. Since Authentic Lab has few attributes incorporated, the analysis was restricted to the testing of those elements alone. Researchers can use relatively tricky concepts and a different field of knowledge in future.

The researchers on similar footprints can also work on the disadvantages of the e-learning systems, especially the problems with technology and its adaptation. A user-friendly user interface and least interaction with the industrial setting can make the process of e-learning smooth for the learner.

5. Conclusion

E-learning is the use of technology instruments in conventional or unconventional classrooms, whereas authentic learning is the approach of using those tools. Therefore, e-learning is focused on the use of technology; on the other hand, authentic learning is focused on learners' cognitive enhancement utilising technology and other tools. Authentic learning is dynamic because this mode of education enables the student to turn the information into practical and useful knowledge. According to cognitive scientists, three principles help in aligning the learning research and authentic learning; the learners look for connecting other learners, the expertise comes from practice, and students are enticed to explore the latest context of the theory and practice. Many educational psychologists and researchers have studied the outcomes of introducing e-learning based authentic environment. Technology can be supported in an education system at the expense of conceding cognitive abilities. Thus, the best approach for the inclusion of e-learning into higher school and college-level systems is the adoption of the authentic method. This study is based on the application of authentic principles in the domain of e-learning frameworks. Among many attributes of authentic learning, the "use of real-world

problems" to relate the concepts was used. The combination of e-learning with authentic approach lead to the creation of an application that presented the user motivation to learn the ideas (because the problems were based on real-life situations), provided exploration potential (the concepts were associated with different levels of information, including infographics and video aids) and exhibited comprehensive information. After getting the respondents to use the application, an online survey form was presented that was designed with two main parameters repeating over the four sets of questions. These parameters include the ease to understand the concept and the likelihood of remembering the concepts. These parameters were analysed against factors like the age, prior experience of any e-learning application and educational level of the respondent. A detailed analysis of the data showed that both parameters against the given factors showed positive results. Surprisingly, there was no significant change in the results across all the elements. It is obvious to conclude that age, prior experience, and educational level do not have any impact on the ease of understanding the concept and perception of the likelihood of remembering the concepts.

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